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ROLE OF NATURAL AND HUMAN RESOURCE FACTORS IN COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

It is this harnessing of the natural world that transforms natural materials into natural resources, that is, into an asset that can be used to produce goods and services that meets human needs and wants. That is not say, of course, that natural materials are only valuable because if they are used or valued by humans. The natural world has an intrinsic value that was imbued by its creator. But such materials only have value as a resource because of human creativity.

Key words: Human, factors, natural world

Meaning of Natural Resources

Natural resources are useful raw materials that we get from the Earth. They occur naturally, which means that humans cannot make natural resources. Instead, we use and modify natural resources in ways that are beneficial to us. The materials used in human-made objects are natural resources. Examples of natural resources: Air, Animals, Coal, Minerals, Natural gas, Oil, Plants, Sunlight and Water.

In many business usages, natural resources are those things found in nature that can help a business make a product. For example, oil, coal, hydrogen and water are natural resources industry uses to create energy to power machines and heat and cool buildings. Other materials, such as wood and ores, are used to make finished products. Foods are also considered natural resources. The term “natural resources” often comes up when discussing a business’ impact on the environment, specifically the depletion of natural resources, destruction of land and habitat and the pollution of water and air.

Natural Resource Management Defined

Natural resource management is an interdisciplinary field of study that considers the physical, biological, economic and social aspects of handling natural resources. It involves putting resources to their best use for human purposes in addition to preserving natural systems. Natural resource managers' duties include overseeing workers, analyzing data, developing environmental plans and policies in accordance with state and federal laws and negotiating land and resource use contracts with landowners and governments.

Earth or physical sciences involves the chemical and physical properties of ecosystems. This may include the study of soils and the disciplines of geoscience and GIS (Geographic Information Systems). Science of biotic resources focuses on ecosystem management and biological principles. This would include the study of vegetation, wildlife and landscapes. It can include working with farmers in an effort to manage rangelands and protect wildlife, along with working with other agencies to oversee recreational land use. Social sciences looks at how humans affect the environment or various ecosystems.

This area of natural resources management may look to the disciplines of sociology, anthropology or emergency management. Pollution control examines how air, water and land pollution can be reduced and how quality of these resources can be restored. Environmental communication involves the use of mass media, public relations and journalism to highlight environmental and natural resources issues and concerns.

- **Biotic and Abiotic Natural Resources**

There are several ways to classify natural resources, including where they come from and if they are renewable or not. If natural resources come from living things or organic materials, then they are considered biotic resources. Biotic resources include plants, animals, and fossil fuels. The three fossil fuels are coal, oil, and natural gas. Fossil fuels are classified as biotic resources because they were formed from the decay of organic matter over millions of years. On the other hand, abiotic resources originate from nonliving and inorganic materials.

- **Concept of Human Resources**

Human resources is the term -- first used in the early 1900s and then more widely in the 1960s -- for the people who work for the organization, in aggregate. HRM is really employee management with an emphasis on those employees as assets of the business. In this context, employees are sometimes referred to as human capital. As with other business assets, the goal is to make effective use of employees, reducing risk and maximizing return on investment.

The modern HR technology term, human capital management, has come into more frequent use than the term, HRM, with the widespread adoption by large and midsize companies and other organizations of software to manage many HR functions.

Meaning of Human Resources

The people who make and sell your products are human resources. This term most often refers to internal employees rather than outsourced contractors when businesses create their budgets. This is because employees often require more management and compensation than contractors. For example, a business will pay a contractor a set fee for a specific service in which the contractor is expert. An employee might require training, a supervisor, benefits and payroll deductions. The term “human resources” also refers to the function of hiring, training, managing and terminating employees. Because some people consider assets capital, the term “human capital” became business jargon to describe employees. The word “personnel” has given way to “human resources” because of the more all-encompassing scope of the latter phrase.

• Human resource management functions

Areas of HRM oversight include the following:

- employee recruitment, on boarding and retention
- talent management and workforce management
- job role assignment
- compensation
- labor law compliance
- performance management
- learning and training
- succession planning
- employee engagement and recognition

• Natural Resources are Human Resources

As Boudreaux notes, misunderstanding this concept can lead to a misunderstanding of the role of nature in creating human bounty. Believing this mistaken idea can even impede human progress. Many nations, particularly in Africa and the Middle East, confuse their country’s ‘wealth’ with natural materials like oil or gas that is buried in their lands. What they fail to recognize is that the wealth created is due to the creativity of those who turned the material into a valuable resource for powering jet planes or heating skyscrapers. Without the mixing of such material with human ingenuity, their “natural resources” are of almost no value at all to mankind.

Concept of Capital Resources

Capital refers to money or credit used to invest in or grow a business, which can come from a variety of sources. A business plan might list the assets needed to start a company, such as equipment, office supplies, furniture and computers. The investment money needed to buy those assets is classified as capital. An investor will want to know how much start-up capital you need to launch the business, then how much working capital you’ll need to initially operate it. There is no universally accepted definition of capital, with some people including credit sources and

others classifying hard assets you can sell as business capital. Under these definitions, capital resources would include cash, lines of credit, bridge loans, finished inventory, supplies of materials and other saleable assets.

Definition of Capital Resources

When was the last time you went to the mall? Remember all the storefronts, each filled with items for sale? Products available for purchase range from decorative knick-knacks to large pieces of furniture, kitchen appliances to classic blue jeans. It's endless! And, just imagine, each and every one of those goods was manufactured.

some items are handmade and one of a kind. But for those items that are one of many, manufactured by a business on a large scale, a lot of resources are used to bring these items to our storefronts. The resources used vary just as greatly as the goods themselves and include manpower, raw materials, time, and - the focus of this lesson - capital resources.

FROM NATURAL RESOURCES TO HUMAN RESOURCES

The Trinidadians used to boast that oil don't spoil. Burnham retorted that you cannot eat oil. You cannot also eat bauxite, gold, diamonds or timber. Guyana had a lot of these. It still however remained underdeveloped. In fact, it was a source of bewilderment for nationals of the Caribbean that Guyana was so endowed with natural resources – rice, bauxite, gold, timber, diamonds, sugar – and still remained poor. The problem, it was concluded, was the management of the country which failed to exploit these resources for the benefit of the country and its people. But that is putting it too simplistically. Guyanese always have this idea that Guyana is a nation blessed with an abundance of natural resources.

The value of our natural resources however is not intrinsic; it depends on what we do with it and how competitive these resources are in relation to similar resources held by others. Guyana, for example, has always had high grade bauxite. But because of the depths at which the ore is to be found, that bauxite remained uncompetitive when compared to other countries such as China and Russia. Ironically, it is the expansion of the economies of Russia and China that has led to increased interest in Guyana's bauxite.

Resources must have a few key qualities to be considered a capital resource. They must:

Be a component in the manufacturing process and necessary for the process to produce a product.

Be used over an extended period of time. This time frame will vary according to the life expectancy of the resource, but may not only be used once.

Be man-made.

The tools and machines used in the manufacturing process are great examples of capital resources. These items, regardless of what kind of item they are used to make, meet all three qualities: they are man-made, essential to the manufacturing process, and can be used time and

time again over a long period of time.

IMPORTANT FACTORS

Water: To be precise, freshwater. Simply put, where there's water, there's life. Also, depending on your age, 50 – 60% of your body is made up of water.

Soil: Supports plant life.

The human brain: Has the ability of being put to use in order to sustainably manage other important resources.

HRM Development and Implementation responsibilities

While most firms have a human resources or personnel department that develops and implements HRM practices, responsibility lies with both HR professionals and line managers. The interplay between managers and HR professionals leads to effective HRM practices. For example, consider performance appraisals. The success of a firm's performance appraisal system depends on the ability of both parties to do their jobs correctly. HR professionals develop the system, while managers provide the actual performance evaluations.

The nature of these roles varies from company to company, depending primarily on the size of the organization. This discussion assumes a large company with a sizable HRM department. However, in smaller companies without large HRM departments, line managers must assume an even larger role in effective HRM practices.

HR professionals typically assume the following four areas of responsibility: establishing HRM policies and procedures, developing/choosing HRM methods, monitoring/evaluating HRM practices, and advising/assisting managers on HRM-related matters. HR professionals typically decide (subject to upper-management approval) what procedures to follow when implementing an HRM practice. For example, HR professionals may decide that the selection process should include having all candidates (1) complete an application, (2) take an employment test, and then (3) be interviewed by an HR professional and line manager.

Usually the HR professionals develop or choose specific methods to implement a firm's HRM practices. For instance, in selection the HR professional may construct the application blank, develop a structured interview guide, or choose an employment test. HR professionals also must ensure that the firm's HRM practices are properly implemented. This responsibility involves both evaluating and monitoring. For example, HR professionals may evaluate the usefulness of employment tests, the success of training programs, and the cost effectiveness of HRM outcomes such as selection, turnover, and recruiting. They also may monitor records to ensure that performance appraisals have been properly completed.

Conclusion

Business owners rely on a variety of resources to make and sell products and services, including capital, human and natural resources. If you're new to the business world, you might hear these phrases, as well as other related terms such as human capital, personnel and raw materials. Understanding the differences will help you better communicate with the different professionals you'll encounter in business meetings.

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